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**A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF EFFECTIVENESS OF VALUE EDUCATION ON THE
BEHAVIOUR OF B.ED. AND B.TECH. STUDENTS**

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The twentieth century has been a century of unprevented social transformation in human society. We are currently witnessing the emergence of the 'Knowledge Society' in which education will become the centre of knowledge in the 21th century. Acquisition and distribution of knowledge will become central concern of the new knowledge society. Humankind in our times in passing through an age of accelerated transition, changes and social transformations.

Modern scientific and technological advancement and affirmation of democracy as a criterion of legitimacy of governments have tremendous potentialities of deeply affecting the quality of human life in the following period of human history.

Both science and technology as well as democracy are seen to provide a panacean for all human problems of poverty, hunger disease, backwardness and social and political oppression.

Science and democracy have come into the modern world at the same time and they are mutually related as cause and effect.

At the same time both science and technology as well as democracy have produced good as well as had results for the society and have entailed paradoxes and contradictions.

In the work of a 'Knowledge Explosion' which has engulfed the present day education system the primary goal of education for improving the quality of life has been lost sight off. In the formative years when the pupils should be experiencing tender ease in a tension free atmosphere, the school presses them hard to master vast content areas. 'Affective domains' has gradually made it exit from the educational objectives educationist who pioneered the

educational philosophy in the term of the present country, were on the other hand deeply involved with a humanistic ideology and included among major curricular objectives, the nurturance of this equally important aspects of pupils development. They were also concerned with the inculcation of a healthy and desirable set of values conducive to the welfare of a democratic society.

Earliest exposition in the regard (Tagore 1892, Dewey 1896) emphasized the relevance of value oriented content taught in congenial atmosphere. Philosophy of education according to Dewey, had the problem of discovering the value of education in human experience and the place is occupied in the larger, whole of life. Later humanist laid emphasis on the significant learning (Rogers 1961) and intrinsic learning (Maslow 1968) in the content of involvement in subject matter which is related to specific learning needs and capabilities of the learner. It is expected that such human treatment of both the pupil and the learning material would lead to desirable educational outcomes like receptive, open and creative minds and well rounded personalities.

The value domain calls for a two stage action. The first of these is to define what values are and to describe differentiate between various value-areas. Value area is differentiated according to the choice of modes of actions adopted in attainment of the ultimate goals and ends.

Human life is intellectually more powerful than that of other creatures. Man is the superior to other creatures, but his superiority doesn't depend upon his physical powers. Animals like lions, tiger, elephant, and bulls are physically much stronger than man. But besides these factors man has dominated them all. He has controlled these animals by his intellectual power. Man develops both his intellect and body whereas other animals develop their body power alone. Man is the only existence of the nature which comprise with certain values. Value in behavior, actions life. Such valuable behavior leads man forwarded amongst all such creatures therefore it has been popularly said that the "Man is the finest creation of nature".

Certain value made him differentiated from the other existence of god. Therefore it has been very much essential to have certain values in man to became the mankind creator.

ORIGIN OF THE PROBLEM

After independence, India has progressed a lot. In the field of agriculture and industry significant success has been achieved. Not to talk of small guns, India is not manufacturing missiles, big ships, crafts-motors car, railways engines, sophisticated war material etc. In the area of business, India has not enough to export to almost all other nations of the world. It is hoped that with the new economic policy of liberalization, globalization and privatization, she will be able to boost her economic development. With all this progress, India has lost something on the ethical front. Now India has turned to be nation which ranks only fourth amongst the dishonor people, corruption full nation of the world.

“According to a survey conducted in USA violence, frustration, immortality, self centeredness and egoism are rampant in the social set up. A prime ministers, lots of ministers, governors and bureaucrats are involved in different scams”.

In the midst of material advancement majority of population is under the grip of poverty, dishonesty, immortality and corruption. Even when it is a fact that socio economic, socio political and lot of other factors are responsible for such a scene. Even education cannot wash its hands. This may be termed “Crisis of Value” and characters. This value involves value system and we choose the one which is most valuable and desirable.

If further adds that, in the situation that is developing, it is equally important for us to give proper value orientation to our educational system.

The concept of value oriented education is progressed and propagated by NEP of 1986, to study Indian culture and social conditions and the religions prevalent in India from time to time. We see declination in moral, social, cultural and spiritual values all over the society in modern age. Due to this fatal declination in values among the younger educators we are observing continuous downfall in educational field.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

“A Comparative Study of Effectiveness of Value Education on the Behaviour of B.Ed and B.Tech. Students.

Study : Study Means a systematic procedure adopted with a view to arrive at certain conclusion with references to the problem in question.

Value : Values can be defined as broad preferences concerning appropriate course of actions or outcomes. As such value reflects a person sense of ‘Right and Wrong’ or ‘What ought to be’. “Equal rights for all”, Excellences deserves admiration and people should treated with respect and dignity are representatives of values. Values tends to influence attitudes and behaviour.

The origin of the word from the Latin word ‘Vallere’ which reveals out the utility, quality, specialty and cost of a thing. The concept of thoughts, beliefs, attitudes and reverence of human being are assimilation is values.

Value developing sensitivity to the good, the right and the beautiful, ability to choose the right values in accordance with the highest ideal of life and internalizing and realizing them in thought and action.

B.Ed Trainees : B.Ed. or bachelor in Education students are those students who are receiving knowledge regarding teaching professions. It’s a stream or branch of education regarding teacher, students and teaching. B.Ed. trainees are candidates who are enrolled to be educated and get training to become eligible teaches in secondary schools.

B.Tech. Students : B.Tech. or Bachelor in Technology students are those who are receiving knowledge regarding technology. It’s a branch of technology which imparting knowledge of various technologies.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To compare and ascertain the behavior of B.Ed. students having values.

2. To compare and ascertain the behavior of B.Tech. students having values.
3. To ascertain, whether there is a difference in behavior of B.Ed. and B.Tech students.

HYPOTHESIS

1. Aesthetic values among B.Ed. and B.Tech. Student having significant differences.
2. Theoretical values among B.Ed. and B.Tech. Student having significant differences.
3. Religious values among B.Ed. and B.Tech. students having significant differences.
4. Political values among B.Ed. and B.Tech. students having significant differences.
5. Social values among B.Ed. and B.Tech. students having significant differences.
6. Economic values among B.Ed. and B.Tech. students having significant differences.
7. Hedonistic values among B.Ed. and B.Tech. students having significant differences.
8. There is significant difference between B.Ed. and B.Tech students in respect of values.

DELIMITS

The study was delimited to B.Ed. trainees and B.Tech. students of self finance colleges of Meerut.

REVIEW ANALYSIS

Mathur and Bharti (2001) worked/studied over working/non working unmarried families to observe the impact of employment on psychological needs/values. Significant mean difference was found. Nautiyal/Uniyal (2002) examined the teacher value with efficiency of teaching in respect of organizational setup. Significant difference was found on various values. Bhadoria/Singh (2005) studied the value differences between rural, urban, tribal adolescents.

From the above analysis it has been concluded that various value education research has been implemented but the comparative study on B.Ed. and B.Tech students regarding value education never done. Therefore, from the above studies, I got suggestive idea to regulate such study.

Population : The population of this study consisted male and female students of B.Ed. and B.Tech. From colleges of Education and college of Engineering of same group of Meerut region.

Size of the Sample: 203 students of B.Ed. and B.Tech. are taken as sample for this study.

Tools Used : A new test for study of values by Km. Shashi Gilani

Statistical Technique Used : The data collected was analyzed statistically. Mean, Standard Deviation and ‘t’ test/scores of value were calculated.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRRETATION OF DATA

H-01: There is significant difference between the aesthetic value of B.Ed. and B.Tech students.

Table : Comparison of mean scores for aesthetic values of B.Ed. and B.Tech students.

S.No.	Samples from	N	Mean Scores	Standard Deviation	‘t’ Value	Result/ Significance
1.	B.Ed.	102	36.81	5.41		
2.	B.Tech.	101	36.59	5.74	0.78	Rejected

Df= 201

The ‘t’ table is used to observe ‘t’ value at df 201 at 0.05 level of significance. The above table shows that the mean scores of B.Ed. trainees more than the B.Tech students. But the calculated value of ‘t’ which is 0.78 is lesser than table value of ‘t’ which is 1.97 at 0.05 significance level. Therefore the research hypothesis is rejected. Therefore it may be interpreted that there is no significant difference between the B.Ed. and B.Tech. students for the aesthetic value.

H-02: There is significant difference between the theoretical value of B.Ed. and B.Tech students.

Table : Comparison of mean scores for theoretical values of B.Ed. and B.Tech students.

S.No.	Samples from	N	Mean Scores	Standard Deviation	‘t’ Value	Result/ Significance
1.	B.Ed.	102	41.86	4.02		
2.	B.Tech.	101	41.24	4.09	1.08	Rejected

Df= 201

The 't' table is used to observe 't' value at df 201 at 0.05 level of significance. The 't' value, calculated which is 1.08 is lesser than the table value, which is 1.97. Therefore it may be interpreted that the research hypothesis is rejected. Therefore is may interpreted that there is no significant difference between the B.Ed. and B.Tech. students for theoretical value.

H-03: There is significant difference between the religious value of B.Ed. and B.Tech students.

Table : Comparison of mean scores for religious values of B.Ed. and B.Tech students.

S.No.	Samples from	N	Mean Scores	Standard Deviation	't' Value	Result/ Significance
1.	B.Ed.	102	40.33	5.23		
2.	B.Tech.	101	40.02	4.65	0.65	Rejected

Df= 201

The 't' table is used to observe 't' value at df 201 at 0.05 significance level. The above table shows the lesser difference between the mean scores of B.Ed. trainees and B.Tech. students. The calculated value of 't' is lesser than the table value of 't' at 0.05 level of significances. Hence the research hypothesis rejects. Therefore it may be interpreted that there is no significant difference of religious values among B.Ed. trainees and B.Tech. students.

H-04: There is significant difference between the political value of B.Ed. and B.Tech students.

Table : Comparison of mean scores for political values of B.Ed. and B.Tech students.

S.No.	Samples from	N	Mean Scores	Standard Deviation	't' Value	Result/ Significance
1.	B.Ed.	102	31.98	5.42		
2.	B.Tech.	101	34.34	6.103	2.91	Accept

Df= 201

The above table shows that the mean scores of B.Tech. students are higher than the B.Ed. trainees. The 't' value after observing the 't' table at 0.05 level of significance at of 201 is 1.97 and calculated value of 't' is 2.91 which is higher than table value. Therefore the research

hypothesis accepted. Hence it may interpreted that there is significant difference of political value among B.Ed. trainees and B.Tech. students.

H-05: There is significant difference between the social value of B.Ed. and B.Tech students.

Table : Comparison of mean scores for social values of B.Ed. and B.Tech students.

S.No.	Samples from	N	Mean Scores	Standard Deviation	't' Value	Result/Significance
1.	B.Ed.	102	42.57	6.28		
2.	B.Tech.	101	44.03	4.34	2.37	Accept

Df= 201

The above table shows that the mean scores of B.Tech. students are higher than B.Ed. trainees. The calculated 't' value is 2.37 which is higher than the table value of 't' at 0.05 level of significance which is 1.97 hence the research hypothesis is accepted. It may interpreted that there is significant difference of social values among B.Ed. and B.Tech students.

H-06: There is significant difference between the economical value of B.Ed. and B.Tech students.

Table : Comparison of mean scores for economical values of B.Ed. and B.Tech students.

S.No.	Samples from	N	Mean Scores	Standard Deviation	't' Value	Result/Significance
1.	B.Ed.	102	38.24	4.44		
2.	B.Tech.	101	37.71	3.78	0.92	Rejected

Df= 201

The above table shows the mean scores of economic values. In which B.Tech. mean scores are higher than B.Ed. The calculated value of 't' is 0.92 which is less the table value of 't' at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the research hypothesis is not accepted. Hence it may be interpreted that there is no significant difference shown among B.Ed. trainees and B.Tech. students on economic values.

H-07: There is significant difference between the Hedionistic value of B.Ed. and B.Tech students.

Table : Comparison of mean scores for Hedionistic values of B.Ed. and B.Tech students.

S.No.	Samples from	N	Mean Scores	Standard Deviation	't' Value	Result/ Significance
1.	B.Ed.	102	35.90	5.29		
2.	B.Tech.	101	33.89	5.22	2.73	Accept

Df= 201

From the above table it has been clearly shown that mean scores of B.Tech. students are higher than B.Ed. trainees. The calculated value of 't' is 2.73 which is higher than the table value of 't' is 1.97 at 0.05 significance level. Hence it may interpreted that there is significant difference between B.Ed. trainees and B.Tech. students hedionstic value.

H-08: There is significant difference between value of B.Ed. and B.Tech students.

Table : Comparison of mean scores on total values of B.Ed. and B.Tech students.

S.No.	Samples from	N	Mean Scores	Standard Deviation	't' Value	Result/ Significance
1.	B.Ed.	102	266.67	20.27		
2.	B.Tech.	101	268.58	22.07	0.644	Rejected

Df= 201

The above table shows that the mean scores of B.Tech. students are higher than B.Ed. trainees. The calculated value of 't' is 0.644 and the table value at 0.05 level of significance is 1.97. Hence the calculated value is lesser than table value which shown that the research hypothesis is not accepted. Therefore it quite clear that there is no significant difference between B.Ed. trainees and B.Tech. students in regards of total values.

CONCLUSION

After an critical analysis it has been shown or concluded clearly that the behavior of the B.Ed and B.Tech students doesn't show any significant difference regarding values. Some of the

values shown more or less difference but conclusion made that there is no significant difference between these two groups. As we assumed previously that there is less effectiveness of value education on the behavior of B.Tech students. But such thing proved wrong practically. Such analysis moreover or less or showed that value education also effect the behavior of B.Tech students. It is not only consistent over the B.Ed. students. We can say that principally it showed but practically it is not proved. Both the groups students has an effect of value education on their behavior. It was assumed initially, that the behavior of B.Tech students shows less value on the other hand B.Ed. students has more value fulfilled behavior. But this assumption is not quiet correct. In some of the dimensions B.Tech. students proved themselves to have a behavior fulfilled with values.

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